

EFFECT OF LAMINATE B-STAGING ON OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE COMPOSITE REPAIR

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre composites are increasingly used in primary aircraft structures in order to reduce the weight to meet strict emission targets. However, providing reliable composite repair processes to support the operation of these new generation aircraft is a challenge for the MRO industry. In this work, a double vacuum debulking process is evaluated for manufacturing high quality composite repairs using conventional prepreg materials in an out-of-autoclave scenario with standard hotbonding and vacuum bagging systems. The demonstrated process was able to reduce the average repair void content from 13.1% to 0.0% through the addition of an extra pre-processing step prior to curing. The essentially void-free repair results in a repair strength that is 74% of the parent material strength, demonstrating a 66% increase over the benchmark open-hole tensile strength and 19% increase over a standard hotbonding cured repair. The importance of the volatile escape path and repair geometry is also established, and the findings demonstrate the limitations of using repair patch properties to estimate the repair strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon reinforced polymer composites have been replacing traditional metallic alloys in primary load carrying aircraft structures to a significant extent. The newest aircraft designs such as the Airbus 350XWB and Boeing 787 Dreamliner have approximately 50% or more advanced composite by weight [1]. Carbon fibre composites have many advantages over traditional metal alloys such as high specific stiffness and strength. However, the repair process for composite primary structures as found in the fuselage and wing structures is a significantly different and a more challenging venture for many maintenance and repair companies, given the critical nature of these components. Furthermore, the repair process can be highly operator and environment dependent as repair is generally performed directly on the aircraft under out-of-autoclave processing conditions.

The double vacuum debulking (DVD) process was first demonstrated in the 1980's as a procedure to reduce porosity and improve the mechanical properties of composites manufactured out-of-autoclave [2]. The process applies a second vacuum in a rigid enclosure over a standard vacuum bag set up to reduce the compaction force, while applying a thermal cycle to B-stage cure the prepreg. The lower compaction force allows volatiles and air pockets to be removed as the temperature is increased. Technical papers published by several authors have reported reduced void contents down to a few percentage for various types of resin systems [3-5].

The DVD process has been proven as a viable patch preparation method for the repair of aerospace primary structures such as the Boeing 787 fuselage. Both the aircraft and process are relatively new and several unknown factors exist, which presents a major challenge to the MRO companies. There is also room for improvement given the wide range of composite materials and complexity of aircraft structures. Several commercial DVD systems already exist [6] and temporary DVD structures can be constructed from lumber [7] for single use, however the process can still be time-consuming.

In this study, the quality of an out-of-autoclave soft patch scarf repair using the double vacuum debulking (DVD) process was evaluated and compared to the standard hotbonding repair process. The key factors that contribute to the improved repair quality and corresponding mechanical properties were identified.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE

A standard aerospace grade carbon fibre/epoxy system formulated for autoclave processing (Cycom 970/PWC T300 in 3K plain weave woven form) was used for the both parent and repair patch. The film adhesive was (Henkel PL7000) co-cured with the patch. Both parent and repair utilized an 8-ply 0/90° layup. The autoclave panels used for repair quality evaluation were machined to a scarf angle of 2°. Composite repair patches were cured at 355°F for 150 minutes with a heat blanket controlled by a Wichitech HB-2 hotbonder with five thermocouples. The DVD set up and cure cycle are shown in Figure 1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: (a) Double vacuum debulking set up and (b) cure cycle

Once the DVD chamber has been sealed, the vacuum level in the upper chamber is increased to within 1 inHg of the lower bag, and the temperature is raised to 93°C for 60 mins. After the DVD process, the patch is transferred to the scarfed panel and cured at 177°C for 150 mins using a standard vacuum bagging layup.

Porosity measurements were obtained by analysis of images obtained by optical microscope. The samples were first mounted in cold curing epoxy and then polished. To obtain the mechanical properties of the manufactured composites, the panels were cut into tensile, four point bend and short beam shear test specimens, in accordance with ASTM D3039, D790 and D2344 respectively, using a high pressure waterjet.

Representative 2D repair specimen coupons of 50.8 mm width were manufactured with a scarf angle of 2° and a gap of 25 mm, as shown in Figure 2. Glass fibre end tabs were bonded to the specimens using an epoxy paste adhesive (Araldite 2015). The specimens were then tested on an Instron 5982 universal test machine at 1 mm/min.

Figure 2: Typical peel test load versus extension curve

3 RESULTS

3.1 Prepreg tack

Thermal analysis by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) reveals that a solvent content of approximately 0.15 wt% remains in the as-received prepreg. Following the DVD process, the solvent level is reduced as evident from peel tests performed on the uncured prepreg [8]. The removal of the residual solvent by the DVD pre-treatment has an immediate effect of decreasing the prepreg level of tack. This was measured by a peel test as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Typical peel test load versus extension curve

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements taken show that the degree of cure after the DVD pre-treatment was minimal. Thus the significant reduction in peel tack is attributed mainly to solvent removal rather than over-curing. The reduction in tack can cause issues during the placement of the patch lay-up in some cases as plies may move following alignment; however, the remaining tack in the current material was found to be sufficient to adhere to itself and the parent surface.

3.2 Porosity analysis

The porosity of the autoclave manufactured laminate was measured to be 0% based on evaluation of polished cross-sections at various locations within the material. The hotbonding process, which does not involve any additional DVD B-staging of the laminate, results in repair patches with a porosity of $3.1 \pm 1.5\%$ as shown in Figure 4(a). Additional B-staging of the laminate during the DVD process removes residual solvents and other volatiles that remain in the uncured prepreg, as shown by the low porosity of $0.2 \pm 0.1\%$ in Figure 4(b). The low porosity in the DVD pre-processed laminate meets the aircraft manufacturer's requirements for use in primary structures.

Interestingly, when compared to a repair scenario where the prepreg is cured directly onto the parent material together with a film adhesive, the hotbonding process results in a significantly increased porosity of up to 15% in both the prepreg and adhesive (see Figure 4(c)).

Figure 4: Optical microscopy images of carbon fibre laminates and repairs after different pretreatments

It is postulated that the presence of the film adhesive and scarfed parent material effectively blocks the path for the volatiles in the prepreg to escape. Differential scanning calorimetry was used to study the cure characteristics and rheology was used to measure the viscosity of the materials as the temperature was increased. As shown in Figure 5, the film adhesive starts curing at a lower temperature than the prepreg (100°C vs 120°C) and starts to develop modulus at 120°C. In comparison, the prepreg starts to develop modulus at approximately 170°C.

Figure 5: Heat flow and viscosity of prepreg and film adhesive during cure cycle

The analyses results indicate that the lower surface of the repair, where the film adhesive is applied, will harden and therefore trap volatiles at an early stage of the cure. This effect is illustrated in Figure 6 and demonstrated by applying the additional DVD step in the repair manufacturing process to remove the volatiles in the prepreg, which then again reduces the porosity to ~0% as shown in Figure 4(d).

Figure 6: Illustration of vacuum path for volatiles to escape in a laminate and repair scenario.

3.3 Laminate properties

The laminate tensile and flexural properties are shown in Figure 7. Both the tensile and flexural moduli did not change with the different curing methods as they are predominantly fibre dominated properties. Firstly, it was noted that there was little correlation between the tensile strength and the porosity. This is due to the sensitivity of the tensile test to minor misalignments. The autoclave cured laminates have higher strength due to the higher fibre volume fraction achievable. The flexural tests reveal more significant differences, where it was noted that the presence of only 3.1% of porosity is sufficient to reduce the flexural strength by 10% and interlaminar shear strength by 33%, compared to the autoclave manufactured laminate. The use of the DVD pre-treatment was able to recover the flexural and interlaminar shear strength by 25% and 33%, respectively. This demonstrates the capability of using the DVD pre-processing method to manufacture essentially void-free composite structures with near autoclave properties in an out-of-autoclave process.

Figure 7: Tensile and flexural properties of laminates manufactured by different methods.

3.4 Repair properties

The 2D repair strengths can be compared to the parent material and the open-hole strength as two separate benchmarks, as shown in Figure 8. The open-hole tensile strength was measured to be 45% of the parent material strength. Deviations from typical circular stress concentration factors occur due to the given lay-up and resulting orthotropic material properties. The application of a soft patch repair by hotbonding increased this strength by 40%, which corresponds to a strength value that is 63% of the parent material. The DVD process was able to further increase the strength by 19%, corresponding to a strength value that is 74% of the parent material. The 2D repair strength exceeds the open-hole tensile strength by a significant margin and meets the manufacturer's requirements for a successful primary structure repair.

Although the specimen was observed to be essentially void-free as shown in Figure 4(d), the strength did not recover to the original strength of the parent material due to other considerations such as resin-rich pockets surrounding the adhesive layer, adhesive layer thickness variations, fibre misalignment and discontinuous fibres. These factors contribute to stress concentrations in the repair, which was exemplified by the failure mode which occurred towards the end of the scarf overlap and propagated through the repair patch. The mismatch of findings between the repair and laminate properties in terms of strength and porosity demonstrates the inability of simple coupon tests on patch materials to serve as the only key factor to qualify repair strength and quality. To-date, 2D repair coupons and full 3D repair tests remain important for repair testing.

Figure 8: Tensile strengths of repaired specimens compared with benchmark parent and open-hole tension.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The out-of-autoclave repair of a carbon fibre reinforced plastic laminate structure with void-free features was demonstrated using the double vacuum debulking (DVD) process. The soft patch repairs were performed using standard hotbonding equipment and consumables, and a scarf angle of 2° was machined on autoclave laminates. The only additional requirement for performing DVD is a rigid enclosure or strongback to enable a second vacuum system on top of the vacuum bagging layout.

The quality of the composites manufactured by hotbonding and DVD processes were measured by porosity analysis of optical micrographs taken from cross-sections of the laminates and repairs. When only hotbonding was used, the laminates have an average void content of 3.1%, whereas the repairs have a significantly higher void content of 13.1% with voids present in both adhesive film and repair patch. This was attributed to the presence of the film adhesive and parent material in the repair scenario, which restricts the volatile flow path. The presence of just 3.1% void content was enough to reduce the flexural and interlaminar shear strengths by 10% and 33%, respectively. The use of DVD to reduce void content recovered the laminate strength to achieve autoclave properties.

The hotbonding cured soft patch repair increased the repair strength by 40% above the open-hole tension strength. By applying the DVD process to remove porosity, a further increase of 19% in repair strength was realized, corresponding to a strength value that is 74% of the parent material. Other factors such as resin-rich pockets, fibre misalignment and discontinuous fibres contribute to the reduced strength which cannot be recovered in such a repair configuration. This effect demonstrates the limitation of using patch only properties to estimate the quality of a repair.

The work presented in this paper validates the recommended methodology for industry to adopt high quality composite repairs to support the operation of advanced carbon fibre composite aircraft. Repairs performed with the DVD process have low porosity and exceed the open-hole tensile strength, thus meeting the requirements for primary structure repair as set by OEMs. Further work will be carried out to extend the coupon level test specimens to a round scarf repair in order to fully characterize the repair quality and strength.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.B. Katnam, L.F.M. Da Silva and T.M. Young, Bonded repair of composite aircraft structures: A review of scientific challenges and opportunities, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, **61**, 2013 pp. 26-42 (doi: [10.1016/j.paerosci.2013.03.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2013.03.003)).
- [2] L.B. Buckley, R.E. Trabocco and E.L. Rosenzweig, *Non-autoclave processing for composite material repair*, Report No. NADC-83084-60, Naval Air Warfare Center, Warminster, PA, 1983.
- [3] T.H. Hou, B.J. Jensen and P.M. Hergenrother, Processing and properties of IM7/PETI composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **30**, 1996, pp. 109-122 (doi: [10.1177/002199839603000107](https://doi.org/10.1177/002199839603000107)).
- [4] T.H. Hou and B.J. Jensen, Double-vacuum-bag technology for volatile management in composite fabrication, *Polymer Composites*, **29**, 2008, pp. 906-914 (doi: [10.1002/pc.20475](https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.20475)).
- [5] A.N. Rider, A.A. Baker, C.H. Wang and G. Smith, An enhanced vacuum cure technique for on-aircraft repair of carbon-bismaleimide composites, *Applied Composite Materials*, **18**, 2011, pp. 231-251 (doi: [10.1007/s10443-010-9148-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10443-010-9148-9)).
- [6] Heatcon, *HCS7600-02 - Double Vacuum Debulking Chamber (DVDC) – HEATCON*, Available from: <https://www.heatcon.com/product/hcs7600-02-double-vacuum-debulking-chamber> [Accessed 12 May 2017].
- [7] J. Lombardo, *Boeing AERO*, Quarter 04, 2014.
- [8] S.L. Agius and B.L. Fox, Rapidly cured out-of-autoclave laminates: Understanding and controlling the effect of voids on laminate fracture toughness. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **73**, 2015, pp. 186-194 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.02.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.02.023)).